

Article: Working inclusively with families and communities

Introduction

A child and his family bring in a vast amount of knowledge and experiences that shape their views and decisions. This is the concept of ‘funds of knowledge’, as explained by Gonzalez, Moll & Amanti (2005, pp. 9-10). To be a part of the teaching community is to be aware of this concept that children and their families, communities and cultures shape their life experiences and a quality teaching practice involves working with parents and families in collaboration. “People are competent and have knowledge” (Gonzalez, Moll & Amanti, 2005, pp. 9-10). EYLF (Early Years Learning Framework) also re-establishes the importance of having effective and reciprocal partnerships with families and communities to provide children with the best possible learning experiences, opportunities for them to grow and achieve a successful outcome in life (Australian Government Department of Education. [AGDE](2022, p15). Therefore, this essay focuses on inclusive practices involving families and communities in early childhood settings and comparison between proposed approaches and past approaches for a better understanding.

Approach 1 : Relational interdependence

Removing hierarchy in childcare practices and decisions and working towards collective aspirations and goals is one of the most effective and modern way of including families in children’s learning and development. This means all the stakeholders that are affected by decision making process are interdependent and equals. McDowall Clark and Murray (2012) penned down this as a leadership style approach where one stakeholder that gets affected by the decision making process (example - teacher) is not on an above hierarchy level than the other stakeholder (parent).

In this concept, teachers should not believe that their professional skill and knowledge is of higher priority than the funds of knowledge children’s families possess. This means believing what families have to say about their children’s growth and development. In practice this can look like welcoming immigrant families and multicultural families with a belief that their skills, knowledge, cultures, languages and beliefs are equally important as those of others and should be part of a child’s daily life and learning. Important information like patterns, passions, skills, beliefs, ideologies, and well-being is best understood by the families and

communities and this information is a valuable treasure that can help educators plan for children's future (Michael-Luna, 2013). To practice relational interdependence, educators and institutes need to value parent's and communities decision along with their own pre-requisite ideas of learning rather than imposing their ideas on families.

To implement this, teachers can sit down with families in the initial stages of children's learning and enrollment, discuss with them their beliefs, previous experiences, goals and aspirations for their children with a viewpoint of the families being the 'best teachers of lifelong skills' for the child. In practice, educators can also create child and family portfolios to learn about background, history, language, ethnicity, beliefs and any important information relevant to child's learning. Regular updating of portfolio folders, quarterly meetings with families, following up with new goals from the families, new and shared experiences, setting up community events and engagement opportunities (such as possible religious or cultural events that may hold value to families) are a few strategies to knock down the classic old hierarchy of teachers above parents and forming an inclusive and interdependent relationships with families and communities.

Teachers should aim at enhancing and supporting family and community goals and values with their own professional research and knowledge. This is further related to a child's specific needs and focused plans for diverse learners (example - children with a foreign language as their first language, religion focused families, specially-abled children including autism, ADHD or delayed learning experinces). Furthrmore, this approach is highly useful to support multicultural familes, aboriginal and Torres Strait families, and Islander communities.

"Respecting diversity means valuing and reflecting the practices, values and beliefs of families within the curriculum. Educators acknowledge the histories, cultures, languages, traditions, religions, spiritual beliefs, child rearing practices and lifestyle choices of families" (AGDE, 2022, P.16). This approach has also been proven to be advantageous to children. Keyser (2006) explains the benefits of incorporating this method of teaching to have positive effects on children including greater social and emotional development including greater mental health, social competence, and more positive social relationships from childhood upto adulthood.

Historical views, Limitations and challenges:

Historically, this approach was not very common in Australia and New Zealand until very recent times, where a lot of mutlicutlural groups and islanders reside. According to Ritchie, &

Rau (2008, p.44), a lot of education groups and centres promoted approaches that included parent voice in children's learning. However it was observed that these models and approaches primarily catered to majority group of middle class white families and communities and often times, these models failed to provide their relationship to connect with multicultural, immigrant, financially lower classes and socially backward groups.

This puts the whole point of hierarchy in education and equal partnerships on question where one group of families and communities influenced rest of the classes, sections of societies and their children's learning. One might also say that it can also be an influence of educational institute's personal ideologies which focused on themselves being above than multicultural, immigrant, financially lower classes and socially backward groups solely on the basis of educational institutes following middle class white principles (Graue, Kroeger, & Prager, 2001). This can also be seen as a limitation, both in the past and in some instances, today as well.

Another limitation to this approach could be teacher's own ideologies not aligning with those of parent's and families. As cited by Powel, 2009, he believed that partnerships often faced challenges that could put a question on whether these were a good strategy for educational learning including but not limited to - teachers having a different view than the parents and upon confrontation, the teachers viewing certain family ideas or practices to be "deficient" or "weak" in comparison to their own philosophy. This puts the child's care and learning being put on sideline due to that difference, thus affecting their development and success. Comer and Fine in their individual work classify this as a barrier to effective parent-teacher partnerships and call it "bullying".

Approach 2 : Equity in curriculum: Incorporating families and communities in assesment and planning

One may argue that relational interdependence is same as having parent's and families involvement in the curriculum. It is quite similar but are different aspects of partnerships. Relational interdependence is what we understand about overall functioning, decisions and practices of childcare and early childhood settings aligning with those of families' and communities of the child without any hierarchy. This is what comes before assessment and planning, it is understanding families and communities.

On the other hand, having parents involved in curriculum means incorporating parent's say in children's planning cycles, daily routines, learning journeys, academic process and areas

where parent's might rely on educational resources and educators for insights on growth and development indicators (Bates, 2016). This means that educators' observations, planning, assessments on learning and skills can/should guide children's development and success while also partnering with families and communities to understand why, when, how and what next part of the assessments.

National Quality Standard (NQS), laid out by Australian Children's Education and Care Quality Authority (ACECQA) (2011) lay a specific focus on partnerships with parents to involve them in assessment and planning through equitable opportunities, access to information, continuity of learning, respect for expertise, communities and cultures. In practice this can look like educators observing children's strengths, dispositions, skills and interests and discussing them with their families to understand where these stemmed from, what influences the child at home, what can be done at home to support these skills at home.

For example: A child's interest in construction and repetitive engagement in building and stacking when discussed with family resulted in educators finding out that the child's grandfather was a builder and often talked to the child. This opens a vast area of opportunities for teachers to plan including planning for child's social-cultural learning, connection to wider world (may refer to Bronfenbrenner's theories), learning child's dispositions and skills coming from construction, and so on. This can be further discussed with families again at every step of planning cycles, providing children with equitable opportunities to learn, specifically based on their own pace and skills. AGDE, 2022, p.17, lays out principles for children's learning frameworks with special attention to equitable opportunities rather than equal opportunities for children. "In doing this, educators recognise that equitable means fair, not equal or the same, and some children may need greater access to resources and support to participate in early childhood settings" (AGDE, 2022 p.17).

Another example of equitable opportunities is children and families with English as an additional language. This is a situation where both families and educators may feel a sense of miscommunication and helplessness where language becomes a barrier. However, this is also a classic case of family needing equitable opportunities and plans to support their success rather than equal opportunities similar to those who speak English fluently. Here, lots of research, resources, training, critical thinking skills is required by the educator to understand her own practice, to make it unbiased, more accessible and more comfortable for the families. One such practice could be involving child's first language and common phrases used at

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home in daycare or childcare settings and repeatedly communicating with families to create a progressive plan to support them.

Teacher's own philosophies, practices and experiences may get challenged when one decides to partner with families that require additional support and resources may turn out to be inadequate, like not having proper training, or not being able find funding for proper support for families. At every step, critical thinking skills is required to analyse that an educator is not merely researching and implementing by herself, but also reflecting, consulting families and communities, looking from different perspective, focusing on child and family's success. Use of journals, parent-teacher meetings, daily dairies, E-portal communication, learning stories, learning milestones, so on are the tools for this practice.

Historical views, Limitations and challenges:

“The concept of ‘we (educators) know what is best (for children)’ is one common misconception that families often have” (Booth & Ibanez, 2017, p.28). In the past, child care and early learning institutes were promising ‘partnership with parent’ based institutes, but these collaborations were quite limited to after assessment feedback and ideology that ‘professionals know the best’. Souto-Manning & Swick, (2006), found in their research that in countries like Australia and New Zealand, where a large group of local groups, Islanders, multicultural and linguistic groups were based, oftentimes education institutes and policies catered to ‘one-size fit all’ approach, resulting in poor success rates and feeling of discomfort among these families. This continues to be a practice subconsciously or consciously at a lot of institutes and among educators where a belief that a standard practice can support everyone in the same way is followed. This is because of lack of understanding, research and training, which poses as another limitation to this approach (Weir, 2013). It is the lack of critical thinking and training among educators. To criticise one's own understanding of how children learn, how different communities view certain practices, what learning outcomes are families and communities look for and need, what are the right and wrong approaches in certain context, meaning of equitable, intentional teaching practices and their implications on partnerships is important in partnership. This emerges as a genuine willingness to work together with families to provide them with best possible outcomes. Powell and McCauley (2011) explain successful behaviour must start with a mutual awareness of each party's responsibilities in the partnership. Training support for educators such as seminars, cultural

competency education, worldview models and their incorporation in assessment and planning can be a great guide to begin with.

Conclusion

In conclusion, partnerships with families and communities emerge from willingness to work together and to build an impactful plan, resulting in success of children and families. For parents and communities this means inclusion, equitable opportunities, hope that their perspective and experiences are not looked down on, rather wanting to feel a sense of belonging in the educational institute. This can be achieved by multiple way, however we have looked on two approaches - relational interdependence (cutting down hierarchy) and equitable curriculum with parent involvement. Both of these approaches share similar history, challenges and limitations and can be addressed by critical thinking, reformed practices and research and training of educators, institutions and government policies guiding the same.

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